

Fundamental Studies on the Interaction of Transition Metals with Carbohydrate Derivatives as Ligands. I. Reaction of 2-Deoxy-2-Amino-D-Glucopyranoside with Salts of Iron, Cobalt and Nickel*

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Glucosamine (I) was obtained in 19% yield as white crystalline hydrochloride from the shells of shrimps available in the local market. Crystalline nickel compound (II) was obtained when glucosamine was treated with nickel sulfate or nickel chloride at a controlled pH condition. According to Job's method as well as from the elemental analysis, the composition ratio of carbohydrate-ligand to transition metal was found to be 2 : 1. Ferrous ions (Mohr salt) and cobalt chloride gave evidences through spectrophotometric studies the formation of adducts with (I) in solution. In both the reactions the composition ratio was also like nickel. Similar compounds, were formed in solution with iron and cobalt salts.

The importance of metal chelates in plant and animal nutrition was discussed by Haertl and Martell¹. Since then, the need for compatible metal chelating agents for use in plant and animal therapeutics are in the way. Since the main problem is to find non-toxic agents that will effectively sequester and translocate metal ions in biological media, sugar derivatives may be worth considering. Sugar derivatives might also be more acceptable for inhibiting metal-catalysed oxidations in processing food and in controlling trace radioactive elements in food-stuffs.

Attention was drawn to suitable α -amino hydroxy or amino carboxylic derivatives of simple sugars² as simple sugars were found to be incapable of forming stable complexes with metals. In our previous communication³ the formation of a stable adduct of calcium chloride with monoacetone glucose phosphorylated at primary hydroxyl function was described. However, since with alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (atoms) having d^0 configurations, the probability of complex formations and their stability were too insignificant, it was desirable to form stable compounds with transitional metals. The atomic structures of these elements are characterised by the presence of d orbitals in the penultimate electron shell which are capable of taking part in the bond formation. The penultimate d orbitals of the isolated atoms of the transition metals are not completely occupied by electrons, and in accordance with the Hund's rule and the John Teller effect it could be predicted that the atoms would have resultant spin and thus resultant magnetic moment; hence

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1. E. J. Haertl and A. E. Martell, *J. Agr. & Food Tech.*, 1956, **1**, 26.
2. S. P. Moulik and A. K. Mitra, Reactions of ethanolamine, ethylenediamine and 2-aminoglucose with the halides of alkaline earth metals. Paper presented at the Chemistry Section, 58th Session of the Indian Science Congress Association, 1971.
3. C. R. Sahu and A. K. Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).

the probability of forming crystalline metal-carbohydrate compound paramagnetic in character.

In this laboratory a suitable sugar derivative 2-aminoglucose was prepared from waste lobster⁴ shells and was used as a potential chelating agent for studies of complex formation with bivalent transitional metal ions. The present study deals with the complex formation of 2-aminoglucose with simple iron, cobalt and nickel salts such as chloride or sulphate.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-aminoglucose, obtained from waste lobster shells, recrystallised, dried and used. Standard nickel solution : $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ solutions of nickel chloride or nickel sulphate in water were prepared and standardised by dimethylglyoxime method⁵. Standard iron solution : $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ solution of Mohr's salt in water containing few drops of sulphuric acid was prepared and standardised by permanganate⁵. Standard cobalt solution : $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ solution of cobalt chloride in water was prepared and standardised by α -nitroso- β -naphthol⁵. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared by standard procedures. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

A Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer with 1 cm. glass cells was used for absorbance measurements. All the pH measurements were carried out with a cambridge pH indicator.

Approximately 0.5 M solutions of nickel chloride or nickel sulphate in methanol and 2-aminoglucose in methanol-water mixture in the ratio of 3 : 1 by volume were mixed. The mixture was stirred for about 30 mins. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.5-8.0 under a pH meter either by adding filtered ammonium hydroxide or by adding ammonia ammonium chloride buffer. The mixture was kept at rest for about 2 hrs with occasional stirring. An excess of anhydrous ether was added to the reaction mixture and stirring was continued for another 10-20 mins. A light blue precipitate soon appeared. The solution was kept at rest for about 30 mins. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with anhydrous ether and then with an aliquot of 30 ml of water, dried in vacuum for about 4 hrs. The interactions of 2-aminoglucose and iron or cobalt salts were carried out in the same way as in the case of nickel. With iron (II) salt the reaction was carried out at a pH range of 2.5-4.5 and with cobalt salts the pH range was 6.5-8.5. In each case the maximum absorption were noted when the ratio of M : 2-aminoglucose was 1 : 2. The compositions in each case were studied by following Job's method. But attempts to isolate these compounds from solution did not meet with success.

Nature and composition of the nickel compound : The precipitate from nickel chloride—2-aminoglucose gave carbon, 27.89% (calc. 29.53), hydrogen, 6.01% (calc. 5.33%), nitrogen, 6.10% (calc. 5.74%), nickel, 12.51% (calc. 12.01%) and chlorine, 14.88% (calc. 14.54%)

4. N. Roy, Private communication.

5. A. I. Vogel, A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, 3rd Ed., Longmans Green, London, 1962.

confirming the composition $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}$. The compositions of the complexes were also verified by following Job's method⁶. Fig. 1 indicates the compositions of the complexes

These confirmed the earlier observations.

FIG. 1 COMPOSITION BY JOB'S METHOD
I NiCl_2 -2-AMINO GLUCOSE
II NiSO_4 -2-AMINO GLUCOSE

Thermogravimetric behaviour of the nickel adduct: The precipitates obtained from nickel chloride—2-aminoglucose and from nickel sulphate—2-aminoglucose were studied thermogravimetrically in an oven with gradual rise of temperature. It was found that in both the cases at 80° the decomposition starts, some sticky material were formed and ultimately these changed into greyish masses at 110° (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2. THERMOGRAVIMETRIC NATURE OF THE COMPLEX
 NiCl_2 -2-AMINO-GLUCOSE

Chromatographic behaviour of the adducts: The compounds obtained from the reaction of 2-aminoglucose with nickel chloride and nickel sulphate was examined on paper (Whatman No. 1, 0.16 mm) in the solvent system ethyl-acetate : pyridine : water = 8 : 2 : 1

6. A. E. Martell and M. Calvin, Chemistry of Metal chelate compounds, Prentice-Hall, New York, 1952.

and on thin layer (silica gel, 0.25 mm) in the solvent system ethylacetate : pyridine : water = 8 : 2 : 0.25. In both cases the results were compared with glucose and 2-aminoglucose. Both on *TLC* and paper, new spots with characteristic R_F values were obtained for the compounds. The results are shown in Fig 3. In the case of iron and cobalt compounds in solution, 2-aminoglucose was found to be separated from the compound on *TLC* as well as on paper.

FIG 3. THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY
1 GLUCOSE 2 2-AMINO - GLUCOSE
3 NiCl_2 -2 - AMINOGLUCOSE COMPLEX

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